

Fatigue strength of non-welded constructional details using the nominal stress concept based on synthetic S-N curves from FKM approach

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ABSTRACT

The fatigue strength of joints or components must be checked in case they are subjected to cyclic loading. For steel structures, the fatigue verification is given by the $\Delta\sigma$ -concept according to EN 1993-1-9 which doesn't consider influencing factors on the fatigue strength. In mechanical engineering, the FKM-Guideline represents the state of the art for the verification of the fatigue strength of welded and non-welded constructional details. Herein, various influencing factors must be taken into account for non-welded constructional details using the approach of the synthetic S-N curve.

This paper discusses the procedure for determining the fatigue resistance according to the FKM-Guideline in the context of structural steel design using results from fatigue tests on non-welded constructional details. The component geometry (stress concentration, support effect), tensile strength, edge and surface condition can be considered by this approach. The procedure is evaluated using typical constructional details (unnotched components, components with holes subjected to normal stresses) and typical edge as well as surface conditions, like blast-cleaning to achieve the surface preparation grade or hot dip galvanizing. Fatigue tests are carried out on components made of structural steels S235JR, S355J2+N and S690QL under the above-mentioned manufacturing conditions. In future, this is intended to result in a more economical design of cyclically stressed, non-welded components and steel structures taking into account the steel grade, component geometry as well as edge and surface condition.

Keywords: EN 1993-1-9, fatigue, detail category, non-welded constructional details, synthetic S-N curve

1 INTRODUCTION

Many steel structures are subjected not only to static but also cyclic loads. These include towers for wind turbines, steel bridges, rack constructions for warehouses and substructures for escalators (*Fig. 1*). For these structures, a safe but also economical design and execution is required. The fatigue strength of welded and non-welded constructional details is defined by the existing notch effect. For welded joints and components, there are several methods available to enhance the fatigue strength with the aim of extending the crack initiation phase. For instance, design rules for high-frequency hammering were included in the revision of EN 1993-1-9 (1). For non-welded components, the increase in material strength itself would lead to an increase in fatigue strength. However, in the 2nd generation of EUROCODE 3 (1), the detail categories (DC) are still independent of the steel grade. For other branches, there are design rules that strictly distinguish between welded and non-welded components. While the $\Delta\sigma$ -concept, according to the IIW-Recommendations (2), applies to welded

components, the S-N curve for non-welded constructional details is calculated considering the influencing factors of the component. In this context, the FKM-Guideline (7th edition) (3) for mechanical engineering or the DNVGL-ST-0361 (4) for machine components for wind turbines should be mentioned. The consideration of these concepts seems obvious, but from the authors' point of view, a simple transfer to steel structures should be carried out carefully. Mechanical engineering components are often manufactured with high quality in series production (e. g. through machining), while batch sizes are often limited in steel construction. Holes are therefore often drilled in the workshop, sometimes still on the construction site and then chamfered. Afterwards, the components are blast-cleaned in preparation for corrosion protection or undergo hot dip galvanizing. In addition to the component geometry with a notch effect, the fatigue strength is determined by the surface and protective layer condition. As part of an ongoing research project (5) experimental and numerical investigations are therefore being carried out on components with holes subjected to normal stresses as well as Cat. A and C joints are investigated. This paper presents 143 fatigue test results on unnotched specimens and components with holes made from structural steel (S235 to S690) with various surface conditions, such as mill scale, blast-cleaning and hot dip galvanizing. The evaluation is carried out using the FKM approach.

Fig. 1. Examples for cyclic loaded steel structures with non-welded constructional details

2 VERIFICATION OF FATIGUE STRENGTH OF CONSTRUCTIONAL DETAILS

2.1 EUROCODE 3 (EN 1993-1-9:2010-12) and further development (prEN 1993-1-9:2023-03)

The fatigue strength of non-welded constructional details in the field of steel structures is verified in accordance with EN 1993-1-9:2010-12 (6). Various constructional details are classified into detail categories. In general, these detail categories already incorporate all factors influencing the fatigue strength within the specified resistance value for the respective constructional details. The specifications of the allowable stress ranges are the result of a statistical evaluation and engineering assessment of international test data (7). In accordance with the approach of the standardized S-N curve according to HAIBACH (8), the S-N curves in EN 1993-1-9:2010-12 (6) are uniformly defined with $m = 3$ for direct stress range and $m = 5$ for shear stress range. The S-N curves apply uniformly to constructional details, regardless of the construction material - whether it is structural steel (S235-S700), weather-resistant steel, stainless steel, or their respective material strength - provided that sufficient corrosion protection is in place. This definition is primarily applicable to the predominantly assessed welded constructional details and does not sufficiently capture the fatigue behavior of non-welded components (7). For the verification of fatigue strength, the fundamental relationship from Eq. (1) applies.

$$\Delta\sigma_{Ek} \cdot \gamma_{FF} \leq \Delta\sigma_{Rk} / \gamma_{MF} \quad (1)$$

Due to more recent findings and a reassessment of the database for the existing detail categories for constructional details in (9; 10; 11; 12; 13; 14), the prEN 1993-1-9:2023-03 (1) has been extensively revised in recent years. This mainly concerns the non-welded constructional details, which from now on are to be subdivided regarding the notch effect. In particular, the cutting and hole manufacturing process for mechanically joined connections, with a focus on thermal processes, punching and drilling represents a significant difference. In the future, a fixed slope parameter of the bilinear S-N curve with $m = 5$ and $m = 9$ should be applied for the direct stress range in non-welded constructional details

with a light notch effect. This is justified by the longer crack initiation phase for these constructional details (15). For sharply notched constructional details, the form of the bilinear S-N curve with a fixed slope parameter of $m = 3$ and $m = 5$ for the direct stress range still applies. In both cases, an earlier transition to the fatigue limit was made by adjusting the limit number of cycles from $N_D = 5 \cdot 10^6$ to $N_D = 2 \cdot 10^6$. The adverse impact of hot dip galvanizing, as discussed in (10), could be quantified in (14; 16) and reliably evaluated for fatigue design by classifying into a lower detail category. Other known influencing factors on fatigue resistance such as material strength, surface roughness and mean stress were considered in (10; 11), but no fundamental definitions for design practice could be derived from the database. The detail categories in prEN 1993-1-9:2023-03 (1) therefore continue to apply equally to a constructional detail, regardless of the material strength and other factors that influence fatigue resistance.

2.2 Analytical Strength Assessment (7th Edition of FKM-Guideline)

The FKM-Guideline (3) represents the current state of the art in the design of components in the field of mechanical engineering. In the verification, the guideline essentially distinguishes between the type of stress, whether nominal or local stress, and whether the component is welded or non-welded. The fatigue strength verification according to the FKM-Guideline (3) thus offers the possibility of a purely analytical or FEA-based strength assessment. In contrast to the assessment according to EUROCODE 3 (6), most of the fatigue-influencing factors are included directly as input parameters in the strength assessment. This comprehensive consideration of these factors in the design enables a better prediction of the fatigue resistance.

The fatigue strength verification based on the nominal stress according to the FKM-Guideline (3) is generally divided into eight steps. The calculation begins at the point of the material fatigue limit of the base material for zero mean stress $\sigma_{W,zd}$. Taking into account all design influences from the real application through the design factor $K_{WK,zd}$, this value is reduced to the component fatigue limit without mean stress $S_{WK,zd}$. This design factor considers the stress concentration factor $K_{t,zd}$, support factor n_σ , roughness factor $K_{R,\sigma}$, surface treatment factor K_V and effects from specific coatings by the coating factor K_S . It should also be mentioned that the coating factor was introduced in the verification only with the last revision, based on the investigations from (16). This coating factor reduces the fatigue limit as a function of the coating thickness for zinc-based corrosion protection systems. Often the load ratio differs from pure alternating loads $R = -1$, so the relevant load ratio must be considered in the calculation by the mean stress factor $K_{AK,zd}$. With the resistance value of the component fatigue limit depending on actual mean stress $S_{AK,zd}$, finally an assessment of the component fatigue limit for variable amplitudes is possible. This verification can be performed for the fatigue resistance of finite life, fatigue limit or variable amplitudes by the factor $K_{BK,zd}$. The fatigue limit for non-welded components made of steel is defined as the allowable stress amplitude at $N = 1 \cdot 10^6$ load cycles. For the assessment of the fatigue limit, the S-N curve is described by a fixed slope parameter of $m = 5$ in the high cycle fatigue region according to HAIBACH's (8) proposal. Furthermore, there are some limitations regarding the applicability of the verification based on nominal stresses, which are listed in the FKM-Guideline (3).

3 STATE OF THE ART ON FATIGUE ANALYSIS

Nowadays, various concepts are available for fatigue verification, whereby RADAJ distinguishes between global and local concepts (*Fig. 2*). Starting from the nominal stress concept, primarily based on fatigue tests under constant amplitude loading (CAL) within the finite life region of the S-N curve, resulting in a component failure due to fracture, the hot-spot and effective notch stress concept were also developed for welded components (17). The two last-mentioned, also component-based concepts use a local stress determination. Material-based concepts include the notch stress concept for non-welded components, the notch strain concept and the fracture mechanics concept. Due to its simplicity of application, the effective notch stress concept for non-welded components according to HÜCK/TRAINER/SCHÜTZ is considered by the FKM approach in this paper. This concept is based on fatigue strength at zero mean stress of the material as the endurance limit. In this approach, all

influencing factors from the component are considered in the determination of fatigue limit, and the HAIBACH approach is applied for the finite life region with a fixed slope parameter of the S-N curve.

Fig. 2. Overview about verification concepts in general (VORMWALD, lecture notes, 2022 (18))

The factors influencing the fatigue strength of non-welded components have been extensively documented in the literature (8; 19). For the constructional details of steel structures, factors such as material strength, notch effect, surface and protective layer condition, as well as the influence of mean stress are particularly important.

4 EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATIONS

4.1 Test program and specimens

The Table 1 contains the test program with the number of fatigue tests. The above-mentioned effects

Table 1. Testing program for fatigue tests under CAL

#	Test series	Material	Thickness t [mm]	Hole-Ø d ₀ [mm]	SCF $K_{t,zd}$	Surface condition	Stress ratio	Number of tests
01	① RS-S235JR-MS	S235JR	10	-	~1.0	mill scale ¹⁾	R = -1 ²⁾	19
02	① RS-S235JR-BC	S235JR	10	-	~1.0	blast-cleaned ³⁾	R = -1 ²⁾	16
03	① RS-S235JR-HDG	S235JR	10	-	~1.0	hot dip galvanized ⁴⁾	R = -1 ²⁾	12
04	① RS-S355J2N-MS	S355J2+N	12	-	~1.0	mill scale ¹⁾	R = -1 ²⁾	9
05	⑤ LS-S235JR-10-MS	S235JR	10	10 ⁵⁾	2.31	mill scale ¹⁾	R = 0.1	12
06	⑤ LS-S235JR-10-BC	S235JR	10	10 ⁵⁾	2.31	blast-cleaned ³⁾	R = 0.1	13
07	⑤ LS-S235JR-10-HDG	S235JR	10	10 ⁵⁾	2.31	hot dip galvanized ⁴⁾	R = 0.1	13
08	⑤ LS-S235JR-24-MS ⁷⁾	S235JR	10	24 ⁶⁾	2.43	mill scale ¹⁾	R = 0.1	13
09	⑤ LS-S355J2N-10-MS	S355J2+N	12	10 ⁵⁾	2.31	mill scale ¹⁾	R = 0.1	10
10	⑤ LS-S355J2N-13-MS	S355J2+N	10	13 ⁵⁾	2.27	mill scale ¹⁾	R = 0.1	13
11	⑤ LS-S690QL-13-MS	S690QL	10	13 ⁶⁾	2.27	mill scale ¹⁾	R = 0.1	13
Σ								143

List of acronyms

- ¹⁾ as-rolled condition: plate with mill scale in delivery condition (A)
- ²⁾ fatigue test to determine the component fatigue resistance without mean stress R = -1
- ³⁾ blast-cleaned with surface preparation grade Sa 2,5 (R_z = 80 μm) (B)
- ⁴⁾ hot dip galvanizing with chemical pickling treatment to remove mill scale (C)
- ⁵⁾ hole drilled
- ⁶⁾ hole machined
- ⁷⁾ an additional n = 5 specimens from the series #08 were tested at R = 0.5 (#08b)

should be taken into account in experimental investigations, considering the manufacturing practice for steel structures. The above-mentioned effects should be taken into account in experimental investigations, considering the manufacturing practice for steel structures. Based on specimens without stress concentration ($K_{t,zd} \sim 1.0$), the material fatigue resistance should be confirmed according to the FKM approach without mean stress ($R = -1.0$). The tests were then extended to include the previously missing aspects of blast-cleaning (BC) and hot dip galvanizing (HDG). No round bars were tested for this purpose. Instead, the hourglass specimen geometry (Fig. 3a) was used, as this preserved the mill scale (MS). Experience from own unpublished tests has shown that roller inclusions can cause cracks, especially if there is a light notch effect on the component. A total of four test series (#01 to #04) were carried out to characterize the base material in the nominal plate thickness $t = 10$ mm and $t = 12$ mm. Using the structural steel S235JR, the mill scale was to be compared with the blast-cleaning treatment and hot dip galvanizing. The structural steel S355J2 was added in the as-rolled condition to determine the effect of the material strength. To determine the notch effect on components subjected to normal stress, plates with a central hole were used for test series #05 to #11. The slim test specimen geometry with a small hole ($K_{t,zd} = 2.27$, series #10) had a higher stress gradient than the wide specimen geometry with a large hole ($K_{t,zd} = 2.43$, series #08). In this way, the influence of the notch effect could be considered. The structural steels S235JR (#05), S355J2+N (#10) and S690QL (#11) were tested as slim specimens in the as-rolled condition (MS) to determine the effect of material strength. The effect of a blast-cleaning process, which achieves surface preparation grade Sa2.5 acc. to ISO 8501-1 (20) and the hot dip galvanization was investigated using the structural steel S235JR (#06 and #07).

4.2 Characterization of base materials

The yield strength $f_{y,obs}$, tensile strength $f_{u,obs}$ and elongation at break $A_{5.65}$ of the base materials were characterized in tensile tests in accordance with ISO 6892-1 (21). Three individual tests were carried out for each batch and the arithmetic mean value was then determined. Furthermore, the chemical composition of the materials in the as-delivered condition was determined by means of optical emission spectroscopy (OES) in accordance with EN 10315 (22) using five individual measurements. For the hot dip galvanized test series (series #03 and #07), a coating thickness measurement of the corrosion protection coating was carried out using the magnetic induction measuring method in accordance with ISO 2178 (23) by means of five individual measurements. The measuring points were localized in the area around the expected failure location under cyclic loading. The coating thickness determined using the magnetic induction measurement method was also validated using metallographic microsections. Finally, the surface roughness of the mill scale in the as-delivered condition and the blast-cleaned series was determined on a sample basis on all series using a laser-optical measuring system in accordance with ISO 21920-2 (24). The following Table 2 summarizes the results of the material characterization.

Table 2. Summary of the results of the material characterization

Series #	Base material	t_{nom} [mm]	$t_{cor,obs}$ [mm]	$f_{y,obs}$ [N/mm ²]	$f_{u,obs}$ [N/mm ²]	$f_{u,obs} / f_{y,obs}$ [-]	$A_{5.65}$ (%)
01	S235JR	10.0	10.08	294.7	416.5	1.41	34.7
02	S355J2+N	10.0	10.00	446.3	548.2	1.22	27.7
03	S355J2+N	12.0	12.05	394.0	545.0	1.38	29.8
04	S690QL	10.0	9.93	821.0	874.0	1.06	11.7

The results obtained from the tensile tests and the chemical composition were compared with the delivery conditions according to EN 10025-2 (25) and EN 10025-6 (26). The observed yield strength $f_{y,obs}$ and the observed tensile strength $f_{u,obs}$ of all materials fulfilled the normative specifications. In terms of elongation at break $A_{5.65}$, all materials met the normative specifications except for the base material S690QL. The required elongation at break of $A_{5.65} \geq 14$ % was not achieved. It should be noted that the ratio between the tensile strength $f_{u,obs}$ and the yield strength $f_{y,obs}$ is expected to decrease with increasing material strength. The chemical analysis of the base material fulfilled the

delivery conditions according to EN 10025-2 (25) and EN 10025-6 (26). Furthermore, the minimum silicon concentration of $\text{Si} \geq 0.14 \%$ to $\leq 0.25 \%$ required in ISO 14713-2 (27) was also achieved, which is important for the formation of the hot dip galvanizing layer. The thickness of the corrosion protection layer applied by hot dip galvanizing was $115 \mu\text{m}$ (series #03) and $153 \mu\text{m}$ (series #07). The measured surface roughness of the mill scale was $R_z = 5 - 8 \mu\text{m}$ for all materials while the average surface roughness of the blast-cleaned series (series #02 and #06) was $R_z = 80 \mu\text{m}$.

4.3 Results of fatigue testing

The fatigue tests included experiments on unnotched specimens and notched specimens. The unnotched specimens with a stress concentration factor $K_{t,zd} \sim 1.0$ (series #01 - #04) and the notched specimens with a stress concentration factor $K_{t,zd} = 2.31$ (series #05 - #07, #09) are shown schematically with the dimensions in Fig. 3. In addition, examples of test specimens clamped in the fatigue testing machine are illustrated. To investigate the influence of the stress concentration factor $K_{t,zd}$ on the fatigue resistance, it was varied between $K_{t,zd} = 2.27$ to $K_{t,zd} = 2.43$. In addition to the illustration of the holed plate in Fig. 3, two further plates with a central hole and a varying hole diameter were tested. For the specimens with $K_{t,zd} = 2.43$ (series #08), the $\varnothing 24 \text{ mm}$ holes were machined in the center of the $95 \text{ mm} \times 700 \text{ mm} \times 10 \text{ mm}$ ($w \times l \times h$) plates. On the other hand, the $\varnothing 13 \text{ mm}$ holes of the specimens with $K_{t,zd} = 2.27$ were drilled (series #10) resp. machined (series #11) in the center of the $35 \text{ mm} \times 300 \text{ mm} \times 10 \text{ mm}$ ($w \times l \times h$) plates.

Fig. 3. Test specimen geometries of the base material (a) and the plate with a central hole (b)

The specimens were subjected to a constant amplitude loading (CAL) with a constant stress ratio R . The upper stresses remained below the observed yield strength $f_{y,obs}$. The hourglass specimens (series #01 - #04) were tested on a 250 kN INSTRON servo-hydraulic testing machine at frequencies f ranging from 6 to 15 Hz. On the other hand, the plates with a central hole (series #05 - #07, #09 - #11) were tested on a 100 kN ZwickRoell resonance testing machine at frequencies between $f = 96 - 115 \text{ Hz}$. The plates with a central hole with $K_{t,zd} = 2.43$ (series #08) were tested on a 1,000 kN servo-hydraulic testing machine with frequencies from $f = 12 - 18 \text{ Hz}$. All tests were carried out in the force-controlled mode of the testing machines. The termination criterion was a fracture of the specimen into two parts or a frequency difference of $\Delta f = 5 \text{ Hz}$ in the resonance testing machine. Specimens with a number of load cycles of $N = 2 \cdot 10^6$ (servo-hydraulic testing machine) or $N = 5 \cdot 10^6$ (resonance testing machine) were evaluated as run outs. In accordance with prEN 1993-1-9:2023-03 (1), at least $n = 12$ fractures were performed in the finite life region in order to obtain a verified reference value for the fatigue strength from the statistical evaluation in accordance with EN 1993-1-9 Background-Document (28). At least three stress level were tested for each series. The crack initiation locations were documented after the test.

4.3.1 Fatigue strength of the base material for zero mean stress

The unnotched specimens with mill scale were tested at a stress ratio of $R = -1$ to directly determine the material fatigue limit without mean stress. This value could then be assessed using the synthetic approach of the FKM-Guideline. The specimens made of structural steel S235JR were in the as-

delivered condition with mill scale (#01), but also in the condition blast-cleaned (#02) and hot dip galvanized (#03). To investigate the influence of increasing material strength on fatigue strength, a series of specimens made from S355J2+N were also tested in the as-rolled condition. The results of the fatigue tests are shown in Fig. 4. The subfigures show the fractures and run outs separately for each series. In addition, the S-N curves with variable slope parameter are shown according to statistical evaluation in accordance with EN 1993-1-9 Background-Document (28) with a probability of survival $P_s = 50\%$ and $P_s = 95\%$. The S-N curves to be applied according to EN 1993-1-9:2010-12 (6) or prEN 1993-1-9:2023-03 (1) with $m = 3$ (FAT160) or $m = 5$ (FAT180) for the base material are shown as a black resp. gray solid line.

Fig. 4. S-N curves of fatigue tests without mean stress and statistical evaluation acc. to EN 1993-1-9 Background-Document with variable slope parameter m and S-N curves for DC 160 ($m = 3$) and DC 180 ($m = 5$)

It is noticeable that the experimentally determined slope parameters, varying from $m = 9.08$ to $m = 22.25$, exhibit a significant deviation from the S-N curves with fixed slopes $m = 3$ and $m = 5$ according to the standards. This deviation is attributed to the absence of a notch effect in the specimen geometry. The experimentally determined S-N curve of series #01 (Fig. 4a) exhibits low scatter and, following statistical evaluation, indicates an allowable direct stress range of $\Delta\sigma_C = 338.34 \text{ N/mm}^2$. The positive influence of blast-cleaning on the fatigue strength due to the introduced residual compressive stress can be demonstrated using series #02 (Fig. 4b). Compared to the S-N curve of the untreated series #01 (Fig. 4a), the S-N curve shows a 69 % flatter slope parameter m and an approx. 18 % higher allowable direct stress range $\Delta\sigma_C = 402.45 \text{ N/mm}^2$ for $N = 2 \cdot 10^6$ load cycles. The negative influence of hot dip galvanizing on fatigue resistance known from the literature (13; 14; 16) can once again be confirmed by series #03 (Fig. 4c). Hot dip galvanizing results in a steeper S-N curve with a variable slope parameter of $m = 9.08$. It also leads to a reduction in the allowable direct stress range to $\Delta\sigma_C = 267.40 \text{ N/mm}^2$.

Fig. 5. Typical crack initiation locations in specimens without notch effect

It is important to note the high degree of scatter within the test series, attributed to shrinkage cracks in the δ_1 -phase, which have a stress-increasing effect in the net cross-section. Finally, it should be noted that there is a positive effect on the fatigue resistance due to the increasing tensile strength of the series #04 base material (Fig. 4d). The numerical comparison of the fatigue resistance at $N = 2 \cdot 10^6$ load cycles indicates an increased allowable direct stress range $\Delta\sigma_C$ of approx. 3 % compared to series #01.

The typically crack initiation locations, which occurred during the fatigue test, are shown for each series in Fig. 5 using red arrows. All specimens failed in the net cross-section without exception. The samples with mill scale (#01, #04) predominantly failed at the edge between the milled surface and the mill scale. In the samples that underwent blast-cleaning (#03), the location of crack initiation shifted more toward the free surface, where the milled surface and the mill scale were before the treatment. In the hot dip galvanized samples, cracking was observed in the milled area starting from the hot dip galvanization. This did not necessarily correspond to the area of the smallest cross-section. The occurrence is attributed to shrinkage cracks in the zinc coating, resulting in a local increase in stress and, consequently, becoming the cause of failure even outside the smallest nominal cross-section.

4.3.2 Determination of the fatigue strength of notched components

The plates with a central hole were tested to investigate the influence of the geometrical notch on the fatigue strength. In addition, the influence of increasing tensile strength on the fatigue strength was investigated by varying the material strength. Different geometries of the plates covered different SCFs. The results from the fatigue tests of the aforementioned series are shown in Fig. 6. The fractures, the run outs and the S-N curves are shown for survival probability of $P_S = 50\%$ and $P_S = 95\%$ from the statistical evaluation according to EN 1993-1-9 Background-Document (28). The DC 90 according to EN 1993-1-9:2010-12 (6) ($m = 3$) and prEN 1993-1-9:2023-03 (1) ($m = 5$) are also shown.

Fig. 6. S-N curves of fatigue tests and statistical evaluation acc. to EN 1993-1-9 Background-Document with variable slope parameter m and S-N curves for DC 90 ($m = 3$) and DC 90 ($m = 5$)

It can be seen that the S-N curves with variable slope parameters from $m = 3.93$ to $m = 10.72$ do not accurately reflect the EN 1993-1-9:2010-12 (6) fixed slope parameter of $m = 3$. Only series #11 (Fig. 6h) adequately reflects the fixed slope parameter with a variable slope parameter of $m = 3.93$. The DCs presented in the new draft prEN 1993-1-9:2023-03 (1) with a fixed slope parameter of $m = 5$ still seems too conservative, as the tests tend to result in flatter slope parameters. The reference values of the allowable direct stress range $\Delta\sigma_C$ for $N_C = 2 \cdot 10^6$ load cycles also show considerably higher allowable direct stress ranges than the DC90 in most cases. For example, the plates with holes and mill scale made of S235JR (series #05, Fig. 6a) - the lowest steel grade in the field of application - far exceeds the DC90 acc. to EN 1993-1-9:2010-12 (6) with $\Delta\sigma_C = 199.22 \text{ N/mm}^2$. In the case of notched components (Series #06, Fig. 6b), the blast-cleaning results in a reduction of the fatigue resistance rather than an increase. This is presumably because the blast-cleaning process cannot

penetrate the hole and therefore positive residual compressive stresses cannot be generated in the area of the largest stresses that occur. Hot dip galvanizing (Series #07, Fig. 6c) also leads to a reduction in the fatigue strength of notched components. As with the samples without notch effect, this is due to the shrinkage cracks in the corrosion protection layer.

The dominant influence factor on the fatigue strength, which is the geometrical notch, can be discussed using series #08 (Fig. 6d). Despite the same base material, the allowable direct stress range for the specimens from series #08 is reduced by approx. 18 % due to the $K_{t,zd} = 2.43$ compared to series #05 with $K_{t,zd} = 2.31$. Series #08b (Fig. 6e) contains fractures that were generated at variable R ratios in addition to series #08 (Fig. 6d). This is intended to show that the structural steel S235JR is less sensitive to medium stress. The S-N curves displayed in Fig. 6e were calculated by statistically evaluating the fractures at $R = 0.1$ and $R = \text{var.}$ together. In comparison to series #08 (Fig. 6d), where only the data points at $R = 0.1$ were evaluated, it can be seen that the slope parameter changes from $m = 6.65$ to $m = 6.38$ and the reference value of the allowable direct stress range $\Delta\sigma_C$ is only reduced by 1.83 %.

The positive influence of the increasing tensile strength on the fatigue strength can be seen in the comparison between series #05 and series #09 with the same $K_{t,zd} = 2.31$. The approx. 21 % higher tensile strength leads to an approx. 10 % higher allowable direct stress range acc. to the statistical evaluation. On the other hand, the influence of an increased tensile strength of the material on the fatigue strength is not noticeable in series #10 compared to series #05. Subsequent investigations, using metallographic microsections, revealed that the drilling was not carried out accurately. This resulted in a large number of cracks and strong strain hardening in the area of the drilled hole. However, a positive influence from the higher tensile strength is not recognizable based on series #11. In addition, this series had a comparatively very steep slope parameter with $m = 3.93$.

Fig. 7. Typical crack initiation locations in specimens with notch effect during the fatigue test

The typical crack initiation locations (red arrows) that occurred during the tests are shown in Fig. 7. The as-delivered specimens as well as the blast-cleaned and HDG specimens predominantly exhibit a crack initiation starting from the hole, perpendicular to the largest principal normal stress. Due to the inadequately drilled hole, the fracture surfaces of series #10 exhibit many small crack initiations, which later grew together to become a large crack front. Series #11 with the machined holes predominantly shows a crack initiation from the corner between the hole and the mill scale.

4.3.3 Findings

The following section discusses the influencing factors on fatigue strength that were significant in the experimental investigations. The geometrical notch has the most significant effect on fatigue strength. A sharper notch effect leads to a steeper slope parameter of the S-N curve. Furthermore, the allowable direct stress range is reduced. Blast-cleaning has a positive effect on the fatigue strength of unnotched specimens, as the induced residual compressive stresses near the surface locally reduce the stresses generated by external loads. The crack initiation phase at the component surface is thus extended. However, this positive effect cannot be observed in notched components. Hot dip galvanizing, on the other hand, leads to a reduction in fatigue strength for both unnotched and notched components. Significant scattering observed within the series with the unnotched specimens (series #03) can be attributed to shrinkage cracks in the zinc coating. A varying mean stress has no significant influence on the fatigue strength of steels with low yield strength (S235JR).

5 ASSESSMENT OF THE FATIGUE TEST RESULTS

5.1 Verification of the fatigue tests using FKM-approach

In the following, the DC according to the EUROCODE 3 (6) determined from the fatigue tests and subsequent statistical evaluation should be assessed. For this purpose, the FKM approach was used for the tested non-welded constructional details. The calculation begins with the material fatigue limit for completely reversed axial stress, denoted as $\sigma_{W,zd}$, which is defined for structural steels as the arithmetic product of fatigue strength factor $f_{w,\sigma} = 0.45$ and the tensile strength. This value is subsequently reduced by the factors influencing the fatigue strength, which are expressed in the design factor $K_{WK,zd}$ from Eq. (2). The Siebel / Stieler concept was used for the calculation of the support factor n_σ for notched components. Considering all effects from series #09 results in a design factor $K_{WK,zd}$ of 2.32 and a component fatigue limit without mean stress of $S_{WK,zd} = 105.63 \text{ N/mm}^2$.

$$K_{WK,zd} = \left(K_{f,zd} + \frac{1}{K_{R,\sigma}} - 1 \right) \cdot \frac{1}{K_V \cdot K_S} = \left(2.04 + \frac{1}{0.78} - 1 \right) \cdot \frac{1}{1 \cdot 1} = 2.32 \quad (2)$$

The FKM-Guideline (3) defines the component fatigue limit for non-welded components at $N = 1 \cdot 10^6$ load cycles. Since the FKM-Guideline (3) and the EUROCODE 3 (6) use the same probability of survival of $P_S = 97.5 \%$, Eq. (3) can be used for the calculation of a DC.

$$\Delta\sigma_C = 2 \cdot S_{AK,zd} \cdot \sqrt[k_\sigma]{\frac{1}{2}} = 2 \cdot 96.22 \text{ N/mm}^2 \cdot \sqrt[5]{\frac{1}{2}} = 167.52 \text{ N/mm}^2 \quad (3)$$

As a result, a purely analytically determined detail category of $\Delta\sigma_C = 167.52 \text{ N/mm}^2$ was established for series #09. In comparison, a value of $\Delta\sigma_C = 170.72 \text{ N/mm}^2$ could be derived from the tests. Table 3 provides an overview of all the detail categories determined using this method for the test series.

5.2 Comparison between characteristic S-N curves and FKM-approach

The Fig. 8 is intended to illustrate the accurate prediction of fatigue strength using two example series. The test results of the series #04 and #09 are presented alongside the S-N curves determined following the FKM approach and defined according to EUROCODE 3 (6) and its revision (1).

Fig. 8. Exemplary comparison of the test results, FKM approach and S-N curves according to EUROCODE 3

There is excellent agreement between the test results and the FKM approach, considering the slopes suggested by HAIBACH. In contrast, the S-N curves according to EUROCODE 3 (6) deviate significantly from the test results. The FKM approach also accurately predicted the fatigue strength for most of the other test series, as shown in Table 3. However, not all test series could be reliably evaluated. This emphasises the point of typical steel structure manufacturing practice, which already led to

results on the unsafe side of the S-N curve for structural steel S235 and S355. This is even more pronounced for notch-sensitive high-strength structural steel S690 from series #11.

Table 3. Summary of the comparison of the unnotched and notched components between experimentally determined fatigue strength and fatigue strength determined according to the FKM approach.

#	Test series	Stress ratio	# data	Slope parameter		Detail category		FKM-Guideline	
				m [-]	m = k _σ [-]	Δσ _c [N/mm ²]	Δσ _c [N/mm ²]	S _{AK,zd} [N/mm ²]	Δσ _{c,EC3} [N/mm ²]
01	① RS-S235JR-MS	R = -1	19	13.12	15	338.34 (360.05)	353.10 (370.64)	157.20	300.20
02	① RS-S235JR-BC	R = -1	16	22.25	15	402.45 (414.80)	377.01 (395.19)	186.79 ¹⁾	356.71 ¹⁾
03	① RS-S235JR-HDG	R = -1	12	9.06	15	267.40 (310.81)	314.38 (344.58)	128.66 ²⁾	245.70 ²⁾
04	① RS-S355J2N-MS	R = -1	9	9.56	15	348.50 (374.82)	380.66 (421.29)	191.20	365.13
05	⑤ LS-S235JR-10-MS	R = 0.1	12	10.72	5	199.22 (210.34)	141.32 (165.39)	81.06	141.13
06	⑤ LS-S235JR-10-BC	R = 0.1	13	10.17	5	177.00 (189.23)	116.13 (153.35)	107.24 ³⁾	186.72 ³⁾
07	⑤ LS-S235JR-10-HDG	R = 0.1	13	5.15	5	128.77 (135.31)	128.60 (133.55)	63.01 ²⁾	109.72 ²⁾
08	⑤ LS-S235JR-24-MS	R = 0.1	13	6.65	5	163.00 (171.77)	145.33 (157.00)	74.25	129.28
09	⑤ LS-S355J2N-10-MS	R = 0.1	10	8.44	5	219.88 (236.31)	170.72 (191.57)	96.22	167.52
10	⑤ LS-S355J2N-13-MS	R = 0.1	13	8.99	5	203.92 (223.12)	161.94 (185.55)	96.96	168.82
11	⑤ LS-S690QL-13-MS	R = 0.1	13	3.93	5	167.30 (182.96)	188.73 (207.62)	125.46	218.43

#data = number of fractures
 (...) Val. for P_S = 50 %
¹⁾ calculated with K_V = 1.15 | R_z = 80 μm
²⁾ calculated with K_S = 0.734 | R_z = 8.4 μm
³⁾ calculated with K_V = 1.30 | R_z = 80 μm

6 SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

Results from fatigue tests on unnotched and notched specimens were shown. In addition, different surface conditions of the samples were considered in the tests. The tests were intended to investigate various influencing factors on fatigue behavior, considering typical steel structure manufacturing practices and their effects on fatigue strength. Important insights were gained into the influence of hole manufacturing and surface conditions. Subsequently, the results were evaluated against normative specifications and S-N curves according to the FKM approach. The comparison revealed clear reserves compared to the EUROCODE 3 (6) specifications. The FKM approach proved to be a reliable method for evaluating most of the test results. However, a secure evaluation could not be achieved for all test results. This prompts the authors to pay particular attention to the influence of steel manufacturing practice for a reliable design. It should be emphasized at this point that the fatigue tests have shown that the series with inadequately drilled holes (series #10) does not necessarily benefit from a higher fatigue strength due to an increasing material strength. Special requirements must therefore be imposed on the execution of the hole manufacturing process in order to achieve higher DCs. The synthetic S-N curve approach can be used to exploit reserves that are currently not tangible. However, this requires reliable findings, which the authors have already addressed in more detail in (29), for example. The mechanically joined connections, studied in (30; 31; 32), demonstrate promising potential according to the synthetic S-N curve, a topic that the authors will further address in their analyses. The aim is to develop a calculation procedure comparable to the FKM approach, one that reliably captures the essential variables for the field of steel structures and, at the same time, allows for a significant improvement in predicting the fatigue behavior of non-welded constructional details according to the EUROCODE 3 (6).

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